

ANALYSIS AND MITIGATION OF CAPACITOR BANK SWITCHING INRUSH CURRENTS USING IRON CORE REACTOR

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Abstract- Capacitor switching in power systems often induces high inrush currents which can compromise equipment reliability and reduce system longevity. This study investigates the use of iron core reactors as a mitigation strategy to suppress these inrush currents and enhance overall power system stability while previous studies have explored solutions such as air core reactors pre-insertion resistors and synchronous closing techniques with varying degrees of success the application of iron core reactors remains underexplored leveraging their high inductance and effective damping characteristics this work proposes the integration of iron core reactors into the switching circuit a comprehensive literature review identifies existing gaps and supports the rationale for this approach a detailed mathematical model is developed incorporating parameters such as reactor inductance capacitor ratings and system impedance to simulate the impact of the proposed solution the model predicts significant reductions in peak inrush currents and provides insights into optimal reactor sizing and placement contributing to improved operational reliability of power systems

Keywords- Capacitor bank, Inrush currents, Iron core reactor, MATLAB/SIMULINK

I. INTRODUCTION

Power quality is crucial in industrial power systems, where continuous operations and nonlinear loads often introduce disturbances. One major concern is a low power factor, which increases energy losses and may incur utility penalties. To address this, capacitor banks are used to improve the power factor by supplying reactive power. However, switching these capacitors can generate high inrush currents. To mitigate this, series reactors are added to limit the surge. When iron-core components such as transformers or reactors are involved, the analysis becomes more complex due to magnetic saturation and nonlinear behavior, which distort current waveforms. Transient behavior is influenced by factors like initial voltage, circuit impedance, and core saturation. Tools like MATLAB/Simulink are valuable for accurately simulating and analyzing these effects.

Thomas E. Grebe [1] examines capacitor bank switching issues and proposes using series inductance and controlled switching to reduce power quality problems. Chris J. Dafi's [2] presents a method to predict capacitor switching transients using a module that analyses system impedance and timing to prevent load disturbances. K. Horinouchi et al. [3] demonstrate that synchronous controlled switching of circuit breakers at optimal times reduces transient over voltages and over currents using a voltage-based timing algorithm. Aaron Kalyuzhny [4] created the capacitor bank switching underground cables back-to-back. The description of shunt capacitor banks, which are widely used in electrical systems to offset reactive power, is finished at that point to reduce energy loss in the power system and conserve power.

B. Sreewirote [5] shows that capacitor banks improve poor power factor at the utility level but face damage risks from inrush current during switching. M.V. Lat [6] analyses how overvoltage protection in capacitor banks affects distribution systems while enhancing power factor by reducing inductive reactance.

Dr. T. Murali Mohan and T. Ramya Durga [7] conclude that series reactors with regularly switched capacitors help control transients and maintain voltage stability. Rui Sun [8] highlighted that shunt capacitor banks improve system performance, and pre-insertion resistors help reduce switching transients. Hessamoddin Jouybari-Moghaddam [9] proposes unbalance protection for shunt capacitor banks to prevent internal failures, transients, and improve system reliability. Vipin Mishra et al. [10] stated that capacitor banks reduce losses and stabilize voltage by improving low power factor conditions.

II. MATHEMATICAL MODELLING

Let us consider a basic electric circuit which consists of capacitor having a resistive load. Basically, capacitors are used for power factor improvement and reduce the losses. Let us calculate the power factor for given capacitor bank rating and load ratings.

A. Capacitor bank circuit.

Fig 1. Capacitor Bank Circuit without Reactor

Capacitor reactive power, $c=20 \text{ MVAR}=20 \times 10^6 \text{ VAR}$

Frequency, $=50 \text{ Hz}$

Voltage: Assume line voltage

$V=132 \text{ kV}$

Resistance $R=1340.30 \Omega$

Step (1): - Capacitive Reactance Calculation Using.

$$Q_c = \frac{V^2}{X_c}$$

$$X_c = \frac{V^2}{Q_c}$$

$$X_c = \frac{1}{2\pi f c}$$

$$C = \frac{1}{2\pi f X_c}$$

$$C = \frac{1}{2\pi * 50 * 871.2}$$

$$C = 3.65 * 10^{-6} \text{ F}$$

Let's double check the value of X_c ,

$$X_c = \frac{1}{2\pi * 50 * 3.65 * 10^{-6}}$$

$$X_c = 871.2 \Omega$$

Step (2): - Calculate Power Factor

$$\cos \Phi = \frac{R}{Z}$$

$$Z = \sqrt{R^2 + Xc^2}$$

$$R = 1340.30\Omega$$

$$Xc = 871.2\Omega$$

$$Z = \sqrt{(1340.30)^2 + (871.2)^2}$$

$$= \sqrt{1795956.09 + 758989.44} = 1598.4\Omega$$

$$\cos \Phi = \frac{1340.30}{1598.4} = 0.837$$

$$\cos \Phi = 0.833$$

As we insert the capacitor bank into a system the power factor is 0.833.

As the above calculation tells that as we insert the capacitor bank into the system power factor is improved. The capacitor bank rating are 20MVAR. The transients are produced in the systems. Now let us see the model calculations of capacitor circuit after inserting reactor to it.

Circuit with series reactor and capacitor.

Fig 2: Capacitor bank with Reactor

$$L = 5.33H$$

$$Xl = 2 * \pi * f * L$$

$$Xl = 1675.344\Omega$$

$$Z = Xl + \frac{Xc * R}{\sqrt{(R)^2 + (Xc)^2}}$$

$$Z = 1674.3\Omega$$

$$P.f = \frac{R}{Z}$$

$$P.f = 0.8$$

By these above calculations we can say that even after inserting the reactor into the system the power remains same but transients in the system is reduced. The current is also remains stable.

III.SIMULATION CIRCUIT

A. Simulation circuit of capacitor bank without iron core reactor.

Fig 3: Simulation circuit of capacitor bank without iron core reactor

The above Fig 3 shows a simulink model of a power system featuring a three-phase AC source, distributed parameter line, capacitor bank, circuit breaker, and an R load. It includes voltage and current measurement blocks. The model simulates capacitor switching effects and evaluates their mitigation using reactors or filtering methods.

By considering the simple circuit as shown in fig 1, here it is a simulink model.

B. Simulation circuit of capacitor bank with iron core reactor.

Fig 4: Simulation circuit of capacitor bank with iron reactor

Fig4, is a simulink (MATLAB) model representing a three-phase capacitor switching circuit with a reactor (inductor) included in the system. This simulation helps understand the dynamics of capacitor bank switching, especially how a reactor can mitigate transient effects like inrush currents.

IV.RESULTS

A. Simulation results of production of transients due to capacitor switching

Fig 5: Input voltage and output current without reactor

Fig5, shows that input voltage and output current waveforms impacted by capacitor switching disturbances. The voltage plot shows a relatively stable voltage waveform, while the current plot reveals distorted current waveforms across three phases. These distortions highlight the transient effects capacitor switching can have on electrical systems, affecting current wave shapes significantly.

B. Simulation results of mitigation of transients with capacitor and reactor module

Fig 6: Input voltage and output current including reactor in the circuit

Fig 6 shows the input voltage and output current waveforms after adding a reactor to the system. The voltage remains consistent, while the current waveforms become significantly smoother compared to the

previous case. The reactor effectively mitigates the capacitor switching disturbances, resulting a proper sinusoidal current waveform across all three phases.

V. CONCLUSION

The use of iron core reactors is an effective and cost-efficient method to reduce inrush currents during capacitor bank switching, which can otherwise cause equipment damage, power quality issues, and system instability. Installing capacitor banks at the consumer end improves power quality and reduces power losses, while series-connected reactors help suppress transients and protect the system. This approach enhances reliability, system efficiency, and voltage stability. MATLAB simulations on a 13 MW load at 132 kV confirm the effectiveness of using reactors in managing inrush currents and improving overall system performance.

REFERENCES

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